

Entrepreneurship an Addiction or Indifferent Behavior ?

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Abstract

The paper's aim is to determine the relationship between entrepreneurship and addiction. Our study findings verify that entrepreneurs demonstrate indications of addictive behavior such as obsessive ideas, duration of withdrawal-condensation, and adverse emotion. Similar to conduct as addictive as gambling or the Internet, serial entrepreneurs may experience adverse effects due to the desire to proceed. The paper will guide future job that requires individuals with addictions to demonstrate that they can perform in distinct fields in terms of conduct or substance abuse

Keywords: entrepreneurship, addiction, mental health

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurship can be said to be of higher significance in the globe, particularly the transition from an industrial society to an information society. Because today the weight of information society on human labor production is reduced, knowledge based on the weight of manufacturing labor is growing daily (Douglas 2006). At this stage, as a complement, innovation, creativity and leadership activities, the significance of entrepreneurship emerges. In the financial arena, entrepreneurship sparkles, it has resulted in speaking about entrepreneurs ' common characteristics. The most highlighted characteristics connected with entrepreneurial individuals in this context; the need to attain, take risks and control locus as listed. Moreover, the attacks are the ability to analyze, to decide quickly, to have confidence, to give confidence and rationality in the entrepreneurial characteristics of people in the foreground (Soysal,2010).

2. Literature Review And Hypotheses

Today, in multiple fields of social science and economic policy, entrepreneurship is increasing quickly and has become a very common field of study. With fast economic growth, finance and technology experience in latest years, the entrepreneur's features have now started to be debated. The fundamental feature expected of the entrepreneurs is that: starting a life of self-determination and independence, working hard and persistent in the pursuit of goals, creating a social network, taking the risk of failure, discovering fresh possibilities and methods to structure and develop the business. Full off a new phenomenon encountered in this process (Spivack, McKelvie, Haynie, 2014) .

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Addiction is a state characterized, despite negative effects, by compulsive involvement in rewarding stimuli. The two characteristic properties of all addictive stimuli are reinforcing (positive) and intrinsically rewarding. The addiction structure was most frequently applied to chemical addictions. Behavioral addiction is a type of addiction involving a desire to execute rewarding non-drug-related conduct on several occasions. Addiction is a disease that is chronic. Behavioral addictions were suggested in DSM-5 as a fresh class, but gambling addiction is the only category included. Internet addiction as a disease for further research is included in the appendix. Developments in psychiatry have confirmed the presence of cognitive addictions that, in the lack of exogenous (i.e., drug-induced) stimulation of brain strengthening circuitry, certain activities such as gambling or video gameplay may be deemed addictive.

Behavioral addiction supporters are mentioned.

- 1) Obsessive thoughts— repetitive, unwanted thoughts, ideas, or feelings...
- 2) withdrawal / engagement cycles— feeling the anticipation and engaging in ritualized behaviour,
- 3) self-worth— is your own view and the value you place on yourself.
- 4) Tolerance — making more resources (for example, time and money).
- 5) Ignore significant friends and relationships, to deal adequately
- 6) Negative outcomes — experiencing adverse emotional results (e.g., guilt, lying, and other people's conduct data). Because of all these patterns of behaviour, entrepreneurship can be a type of addiction. Some signs of entrepreneurship may include obsessing with his / her company, neglecting friends and/or external interests, and experiencing withdrawal symptoms such as rage or anxiety when compelled to turn away from your company, she / he spends a lot of time with company than your family or friends. A construct of personality appears to be 'susceptible to take hazards, workaholic, susceptible to overuse of the Internet.' Is this an addiction to behavior? This study aimed to evaluate in terms of entrepreneurship addiction (Brandstätter, 2011)

3. Methodology

Research Goal

The objective of this research was to evaluate whether entrepreneurship is an addiction.

Sample and Data Collection

This research was directed at reviewing this region by the writers in this research. Authors used important phrases in PubMed, Medline, EBSCOHost, PsycINFO, Science Direct, Turkish Medline, Çukurova Index Databases and Google Scholar to search the papers linked to entrepreneurship, addiction, mental health. EBSCO's first search (Medline, PsycInfo) disclosed 20 articles focused on measuring Internet addiction. The second search on PubMed revealed 15 documents, 5 of which were not earlier recognized, the third search on Science Direct resulted in 14 publications, one of which was a fresh addition, and the final searches on PsycINFO and Çukurova Index Databases produced 2 publications without fresh addition.

4. Analyses and Results

Typically, addiction was used to define a physiological, psychological, behavioral reliance by which an individual is addicted to a stimulus. The book of psychiatric diagnostic criteria for DSM V included excessive Internet use, gambling behavioral dependencies. It is often believed that entrepreneurs are great intermediate gamblers. Gamblers and entrepreneurs show a comparable one based on the danger of having much of their employment (Spivack, McKelvie, & Haynie 2014). Both profiles are aimed at making cash, as well. The entrepreneur and the gambling addict are also accessible for trial and bravery to succeed. The distinction between gambling addicts and businessmen is that gambling addicts are often discouraged from instinct and luck, while entrepreneurs are discouraged from business experience and understanding, goods and data (Clark, & Limbrick-Oldfield 2013; Jacobson, Wasserman, Wu, & Lauer 2015). Behavioral addictions, display

characteristics physical and psychological reliance on primary component addictive concern, variability of mood, tolerance, withdrawal, interpersonal conflict and repetition (relapse) (Arisoy,2009)

Given the hazards, big quantities of dopamine are produced by the brain. This condition creates happiness and motivation for individuals (Schultz, 2010). Several studies have examined the neural correlates of reference-dependence in decision-making. The activity of Amygdala has been correlated with dominant decisions, with enhanced activity for certain decisions and dangerous decisions. Addictive drugs or behaviour, by flooding the nucleus accumbency with dopamine, provide a shortcut to the reward system of the brain. The hippocampus establishes memories of this quick sense of fulfillment, and the amygdala produces a conditioned response to some stimuli. A fresh company that confronts the person is excited about the person when considering entrepreneurship as an addiction and can lead to a rise in dopamine in the person. The nucleus accumbens sends signals to the hippocampus and the amygdala that record and strengthen memories that evoke powerful emotions (Nicolaou & Shane, 2009)

In addition to all these, addiction to entrepreneurship can lead to a conflict with the individual's psychological issues. Exposure to many entrepreneurs gives isolation. This isolation causes an increased danger of depression. Furthermore, many entrepreneurs work lengthy hours, unable to find time to take care of themselves (Dorado, & Ventresca 2013). By working more, entrepreneurs try to mask the symptoms of depression. By working more, entrepreneurs try to mask the symptoms of depression. These symptoms are often interpreted as stress, leading to the condition declaration being exacerbated. Entrepreneurs can also carry a greater risk of suicide, even in extreme instances. Entrepreneurs are under tremendous pressure as well as under stress. The strong desire to succeed leads the conduct to constantly question and upgrade the worst scenarios editing. Anxiety can eliminate many entrepreneurs and cause burnout (Louie, 2015; Meyers, 2015).

On the other hand, businessmen who understand when the loan danger can determine if you need to attempt again and minimize the losses are experts (Pollitt, 2015. According to Phan, everyone has the ability to create thoughts, but only individuals with an entrepreneurial mind, that concept is a step further and capable of translating financial opportunities.

5. Conclusion

Indeed, addiction is the dark side of entrepreneurship. It is essential to have a high incentive to work and generate in company life. But entrepreneurship can be considered as people with behavioral addiction can deliver psychologically disturbing outcomes.

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